

1 Long-Term Impact of Biofilter Layers on Water Retention and Runoff Delay in 2 Bioretention Cell: A Five-Year Experimental and Simulation Study

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7 Abstract

8 Urbanization and climate change present significant challenges to urban stormwater management. Nature-based
9 solutions, such as bioretention systems, represent sustainable adaptation measures. However, there is a scarcity of
10 comprehensive data on long-term performance based on real experiments. This study presents the results of a five-
11 year experiment conducted on a small, isolated bioretention cell as a multilayered system planted with perennials
12 supplied by stormwater runoff from the roof. The monitored parameters included water balance, water retention
13 capacity of the bioretention cell, soil water potential, and plant growth. The study aimed to elucidate how the
14 temporal variability in plant growth and modifications resulting from the development of the bioretention layer
15 influence the retention and detention of water within the bioretention cell. Rainfall-runoff episodes were analyzed
16 to assess changes in runoff coefficient, peak flow reduction, peak runoff delay, and runoff delay. The findings
17 indicated a temporal decline in the runoff coefficient, attributed to increased evapotranspiration and subsequent
18 lower biofilter water saturation at the beginning of rainfall episodes. Peak flow reduction ranged from 30% to
19 100%, with a decrease in efficiency as the bioretention cell aged. The median runoff delay was approximately 50
20 minutes, whereas the peak runoff delay varied from 0 to 100 minutes, displaying increased variability over time.
21 A more accurate estimation of evapotranspiration was achieved using a landscape vegetation coefficient adjusted
22 from photographic records. Inverse modeling using HYDRUS 2D demonstrated a five-fold increase in saturated
23 hydraulic conductivity of the biofilter.

24 Keywords

25 Bioretention cell, biofilter, runoff coefficient, constructed Technosol, evapotranspiration, Hydrus

26 Highlights

- 27 • Experimental bioretention cell was monitored over a five-year period

- 28 • The annual and episodic runoff coefficient exhibited a gradual decrease over time
- 29 • Inverse modelling in HYDRUS 2D showed increasing biofilter hydraulic conductivity
- 30 • Estimation of evapotranspiration was improved by inclusion of vegetation development

31 **Introduction**

32 Urbanization exerts a profound influence on urban hydrological cycles, leading to increase in peak flows by up to
33 fourfold compared to natural conditions (Konrad and Booth, 2005; Moglen et al., 2004). To mitigate these negative
34 effects, there is an increasing inclination towards the adoption of nature-based solutions, prominently including
35 Low Impact Development (LID) features. Such features incorporate bioretention systems that closely replicate
36 natural infiltration mechanisms (Cizek and Hunt, 2013; Fletcher et al., 2015; Shah et al., 2023). LID elements,
37 including bioretention cells, have been demonstrated to retain as much as 90% of precipitation events (Recanatesi
38 et al., 2017), and their application in urban stormwater management continues to gain traction (Davis, 2008; Liao
39 et al., 2017). A bioretention cell is engineered to capture, treat, evapotranspire, and infiltrate stormwater on-site
40 through the rooted filter layer referred to as a biofilter. A biofilter typically consists of a constructed Technosol
41 (Sere et al., 2012), a composite of sand, topsoil, and compost. Although there has been a notable increase in
42 research focused on bioretention cells, the results often demonstrate considerable variability. Nevertheless,
43 relatively few studies have undertaken an examination of bioretention cells as closed systems under comprehensive
44 monitoring, which would facilitate an extensive assessment of their functional and hydrological performance over
45 prolonged durations. For instance, Mantilla et al. (2024) examined a grass swale with an outlet control weir to
46 minimize runoff by improving storage and infiltration. They conducted 43 irrigation-driven tests simulating
47 rainfall with return periods of 1 to 50 years, primarily focusing on reducing surface runoff, while subsurface flow
48 was not studied.

49 Multiple studies have indicated that the efficiency of bioretention cells declines as hydraulic conductivity
50 diminishes, attributable to clogging by fine particles (Coustumer et al., 2009; Hsieh and Davis, 2005; Kandra et
51 al., 2014; Li et al., 2009). Hatt et al. (2009) observed a reduction in the efficiency of bioretention cells attributed
52 to surface moss overgrowth. Subsequent to the removal of moss and the replanting of vegetation, a notable increase
53 in hydraulic conductivity was observed. Different study, conducted by Shah et al. (2023), identified a positive
54 correlation between vegetation growth and conductivity in bioretention cells. In addition, the development of
55 macropores by roots has been shown to increase conductivity (Dudrick et al., 2024; Jenkins et al., 2010; Tang et
56 al., 2016). Vegetation could represent a vital component in maintaining the long-term functionality of bioretention

57 cells. The reduction in runoff and peak flow in bioretention cells is dependent on the depth and duration of rainfall.
58 Smaller precipitation events are typically fully retained (Davis, 2008), but the efficiency of runoff reduction
59 fluctuates with intensity and duration (Johnson, 2020; Li et al., 2023). Johnson (2020) also indicated that older
60 bioretention systems exhibit comparable or superior performance relative to younger systems (less than 3 years
61 old). Furthermore, the initial moisture saturation levels of a bioretention cell affect its retention capability, which
62 in turn influences the overall reduction in runoff. Lucke and Nichols (2015) found that bioretention systems can
63 decrease peak flow by between 79.5% and 93.6% over a ten-year period. However, this efficiency is compromised
64 in instances where prior saturation has occurred. In the case of larger precipitation events, the resultant reductions
65 in runoff and peak flow are minimal (Brander et al., 2004; Holman-Dodds et al., 2007; Hood et al., 2007).

66 Lisenbee et al. (2021) reviewed 11 numerical models used for hydrological modelling or bioretention design. Two
67 of these models, namely GIFT-mod (Massoudieh et al., 2017) and Hydrus (Šimůnek et al., 2008), employ the
68 Richards equation (Richards, 1931), to accurately model flow of water in an unsaturated zone of biofilter. Meng et
69 al. (2014) were the first to apply HYDRUS-1D to two bioretention cells in Beijing. Meng et al. (2014) adeptly
70 simulated the biofilter's response to 33 artificial and five natural rainfall events, yielding results that demonstrated
71 a high degree of reliability when compared to the empirical data. Heckova et al. (2022) used HYDRUS 2D to
72 simulate the direction of flow through the biofilter and sand layer in the transverse direction, thereby enabling the
73 calculation of saturated hydraulic conductivity. The findings of Stewart et al. (2017) revealed that the Hydrus
74 2D/3D model proficiently represented the principal hydrological characteristics of the bioretention cell,
75 encompassing subsurface water accumulation and the augmentation of groundwater levels. The bioretention cell
76 demonstrated a reduction in stormwater backflow into the sewer system. However, this benefit was diminished
77 during periods of high water inflow, when the retention capacity was exceeded. Nichols et al. (2021) who used
78 HYDRUS 1D to evaluate seasonal effects on rain garden performance reported that ponding depth and soil
79 moisture aligned with model predictions. The studies presented indicate that the models based on solving Richard's
80 equation are an appropriate tool for modelling the water regime and optimizing parameters in bioretention cells.
81 Nevertheless, its limited adoption can be ascribed to the model's intrinsic complexity and sophisticated
82 parameterization.

83 Evapotranspiration (ET) is an essential component of water balance in bioretention cells. The Penman-Monteith
84 equation (Monteith, 1965) is commonly employed for ET estimation; nonetheless, its assumption of complete
85 grass cover limits its precision when applied to more variable vegetation in bioretention cells. Although the FAO
86 56 crop-specific coefficients improve the precision of ET estimation, they are predominantly intended for

87 application in agricultural land cover. Transpiration from vegetation is a major constituent of evapotranspiration
88 (Liu et al., 2014). Nasrollahpour et al. (2022), through their study on bioretention systems, indicated that the
89 influence of vegetation on evapotranspiration (ET) evolves over time, ultimately emerging as the most
90 predominant factor in ET as time advances. Costello et al. (2000) developed the landscape coefficient to calibrate
91 evapotranspiration according to plant density, species, and microclimate. This methodology was subsequently
92 adopted by Selbig and Balster (2010) and Bortolini and Zanin (2018). Recent study has proposed employing a
93 simplified crop coefficient ($K_c = 1$) suited for bioretention cells, accommodating plant diversity and local
94 conditions De-Ville et al. (2024). Furthermore, research demonstrates that gravel layers can reduce surface
95 evaporation by up to 85% (Kaseke et al., 2012; Kemper et al., 1994; Meier and Hauer, 2010), in addition to
96 promoting plant growth (Verma and Pradhan, 2024). The actual ET is highly dependent on the availability of water
97 within bioretention cells. A comparative study on ET conducted by Wadzuk et al. (2015) ascertained that
98 bioretention systems with water storage exhibited ET rates of 6.1 mm day^{-1} , nearly twice that of systems with free
99 drainage. The typical ET rates observed in bioretention cells range from 2 to 4 mm day^{-1} , as consistently reported
100 across multiple studies (Denich and Bradford, 2010; Hess et al., 2017; Spraakman et al., 2022).

101 Numerous long-term studies have been conducted on the hydrological performance and water balance of
102 bioretention cells, however these were primarily built on permeable subsoil with exfiltration in bioretention
103 systems or featuring an integrated water storage zone. This research is concentrated on a bioretention cell that is
104 fully detached from the adjacent soil, which is designed particularly suitable for locations such as brownfields,
105 where water infiltration is not feasible. The bioretention cell examined in this study does not incorporate a
106 subsurface integrated water storage zone. The primary objective is to ascertain the retention properties of the
107 bioretention cell's multi-layer configuration, eliminating any delays that an integrated storage might introduce.

108 The principal aim of this research was to evaluate the performance of a bioretention cell over a five-year period.
109 The investigation centered on comprehending the long-term effects of the development of the biofilter's layer
110 properties on both water retention and detention. Furthermore, the study sought to analyze water storage and
111 evapotranspiration by employing a vegetation-specific landscape coefficient obtained through photographic
112 analysis. An additional objective was to examine alterations in the hydraulic properties of the biofilter across five
113 years, utilizing Hydrus 2D modeling, which was calibrated with experimental retention data.

114 **Materials and methods**

115 **Experimental site and bioretention cell set-up**

116 In December 2017, an experimental bioretention cell (BC) was established at the University Centre for Energy
117 Efficient Buildings (UCEEB) of the Czech Technical University in Prague (CTU), located in Bustehrad, Czech
118 Republic (coordinates: 50°9.41797'N, 14°10.19195'E, elevation: 355 m a.s.l.). This site is characterized by a
119 temperate climate, with an average annual precipitation of 500 to 550 mm and a mean annual air temperature of
120 8 °C. A meteorological station, situated 10 meters east of the bioretention cell, is outfitted with sensors designed
121 to measure above-surface air temperature, air temperature at a height of 200 cm above ground level, relative
122 humidity, wind speed and direction, as well as precipitation. The current research builds upon an antecedent
123 investigation by Heckova et al. (2022), which provides a detailed description of the infrastructure. BC was
124 engineered to capture stormwater from the roof of the adjacent experimental building, which has a surface area of
125 38 m² with bitumen roof sheets at a slope of 14° (refer to Fig. 1). The BC study of five water years, beginning with
126 the start of the water year on November 1, 2018, and concluding on October 31, 2023.

127
128 Fig. 1 The experimental site: a) illustrates the building with the drainage roof, the bioretention cell, and the shaft where runoff is
129 measured b) provides a close-up view of bioretention cell 1.

130 The drainage system within the bioretention cell adhered to the specifications outlined in the Czech national
131 technical standard TVN 759011. BC measured 2.4 meters in width and 4.0 meters in length, with a maximum
132 ponding depth of 0.3 meters. A longitudinal section of the bioretention cell, showing the layers and monitoring
133 setup, is illustrated in Fig. 2. It incorporated a mulching layer of 5 centimeters in thickness, composed of 16/32
134 mm gravel fraction, to mitigate water erosion, inhibit weed proliferation, and reduce excessive evaporation and
135 infiltration. The biofilter, with a thickness of 0.3 meters, consisted of constructed Technosol, a mixture of sand,
136 compost, and topsoil in a volume ratio of 50:30:20 percent. A drainage layer, 0.27 meters in thickness, was
137 composed of a gravel fraction of 16/32 mm, and was segregated from the bioretention soil layer by a sandy layer

138 of 0.1 meters thick (0/4 mm fraction) purposed for fine particle entrapment. A geotextile (200 g m⁻²) separated the
 139 sand and drainage layers. The whole inside of BC was isolated from the surrounding soil by a PVC membrane.
 140 The bioretention cell is constructed without incorporating a subsurface integrated water storage zone, thereby
 141 enabling the prompt drainage of water from the drainage layer into the shaft outfitted with a flow meter, which
 142 consequently permits the assessment of the bioretention cell's retention capacity. The inflow water consists of
 143 rainwater harvested from the adjacent roof, where it is anticipated to have a near-neutral pH and low conductivity.
 144 This assumption was corroborated through inflow sampling conducted on May 7, 2023, with samples indicating a
 145 pH of 6.8, a conductivity of 12 μS cm⁻¹, and a turbidity of 1.6 NTU.

146
 147 Fig. 2 Longitudinal section of bioretention cell. Adapted from Journal of Hydrology and Hydromechanics, with permission (Heckova
 148 et al., 2022)

149 Initially, four types of perennial plants were established within the bioretention cell. Specifically, five seedlings
 150 each of *Aster novae-angliae*, *Hemerocallis*, and *Euphorbia amygdaloides* were planted, in addition to eight
 151 seedlings of *Molinia caerulea*. During the spring of 2019, the underperforming *Euphorbia amygdaloides* was
 152 replaced by five specimens of *Eupatorium 'Phantom'*. The systematic removal of dry biomass and invasive weeds
 153 from the bioretention cell was performed in the early spring seasons, and the development of plant growth was
 154 consistently monitored and documented through photographic records.

155 **Monitoring system configuration**

156 The volumetric water content (VWC) of the soil within the BC was systematically monitored using four time
 157 domain reflectometry (TDR) probes (CS635, Campbell Scientific, U.S.A.) that were interfaced with a
 158 reflectometer (TDR100, Campbell Scientific, U.S.A.) through an SDM8X50 multiplexor. These water content
 159 probes were situated at a height of 0.15 m above the sand layer, and the actual VWC (θ_v) values were estimated

160 using Topp equation (Topp et al., 1980), in which K_a denotes the apparent dielectric constant measured by TDR,
161 as presented in Eq. (1).

$$\theta_v = -5.3 \cdot 10^{-2} + 2.92 \cdot 10^{-2} K_a - 5.5 \cdot 10^{-4} K_a^2 + 4.3 \cdot 10^{-6} K_a^3 \quad (1)$$

162 Probes TDR1 and TDR4 were positioned in proximity to the inlet, while TDR2 and TDR3 were located at a more
163 distant position from the inlet. Due to their placement, the probes provide an indication of the soil conditions within
164 the root systems of specific plant species: Hemerocallis (TDR4), Aster (TDR1), Eupatorium (TDR2), and Molinia
165 (TDR3). Water potential was automatically monitored using five tensiometers (T8, Meter Environment, Germany)
166 installed at a 45° angle. The elevations at which these tensiometers measured water potential (via the ceramic cup)
167 were 18 cm (T8_1), 17 cm (T8_2), 9 cm (T8_3), 9 cm (T8_4), and 5 cm (T8_5) above the sand layer. The position
168 and orientation of the tensiometers is depicted in Fig. 2. Furthermore, water potential was measured by two
169 potential meters (MPS-6, Meter Environment, Germany) in BC, positioned 0.25 m above the sand layer.
170 Measurements for water content, tensiometers, and water potential were recorded every 6 minutes. Precipitation
171 was quantified using a heated tipping bucket rain gauge (52202, R.M. Young, USA) with a 200 cm² collection
172 area, providing a resolution of 0.1 mm and recording data every minute. Outflow from BC was monitored using a
173 tipping bucket flowmeter (PF500, Fiedler AMS, Ltd., Czech Republic), with pulses recorded every minute, each
174 tip corresponding to 600 ml of water.

175 **Climatic conditions at the site and soil sampling events**

176 The annual precipitation totals for the years 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023 were 321, 330, 416, 486,
177 454, and 414 mm, respectively. The precipitation data from the northeast weather station in proximity to the study
178 area were analyzed alongside measurements from two additional rain gauges, situated within a 140 m distance of
179 the UCEEB site, which served as supplementary sources in the event of data collection failures. The average annual
180 air temperatures for the years 2018 to 2023 were recorded as 10.8 °C, 10.7 °C, 10.6 °C, 9.3 °C, 10.6 °C, and 11.1
181 °C, respectively. Fig. 3 depicts the temporal variations in temperature, as measured by sensors embedded in soil
182 tensiometers at various depths within the biofilter throughout the study period. Fig. 3 graphically represents the
183 instances during which undisturbed samples were collected from the biofilter materials for the purpose of
184 conducting retention curve measurements. The details on soil sampling will be given in later sections.

185

186 Fig. 3 The biofilter conditions observed over the study years show the average, maximum, and minimum soil temperatures,
 187 ascertained via four temperature sensors embedded within ceramic cups in tensiometers positioned at varied elevations above
 188 the sand layer. The tensiometer cups housing the temperature sensors are situated at heights of 18 cm, 17 cm, 9 cm, and 5 cm
 189 above the top of sand layer. Green crosses denote the specific times when soil samples were extracted for retention curve
 190 analysis.

191 **Rainfall-runoff analysis**

192 The response of the bioretention cell to precipitation events was evaluated over the complete duration of the study,
 193 encompassing both annual and episodic perspectives. Each rainfall-runoff episode was defined as commencing
 194 with the onset of precipitation and concluding when the outflow rate fell below 0.003 mm h^{-1} , as normalized to the
 195 roof area. A rainfall event was classified as precipitation occurring subsequent to a minimum of six hours of no
 196 rainfall conditions (the antecedent dry weather period). Only episodes with a cumulative rainfall exceeding 1 mm
 197 were considered for analysis. The analysis was conducted with a one-minute interval. The criteria for defining the
 198 initiation and termination of each rainfall-runoff episode were based on the methodologies in previous studies
 199 (Heckova et al., 2022; Skala et al., 2020; Snehota et al., 2021). Instances of snowfall were excluded from the
 200 analysis. Snow was identified utilizing a minimum temperature threshold of $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which has been demonstrated
 201 as a reliable metric for distinguishing snowfall from rain in several studies (Berghuijs et al., 2014; Blahušiaková
 202 et al., 2020). Each rainfall episode was paired with its corresponding outflow, to determine episodic rainfall-runoff
 203 characteristics. These included the initial time of episode, rainfall depth, maximum rainfall intensity, episode
 204 duration, runoff coefficient, peak flow reduction, pre-episode VWC and minimal soil temperature of biofilter. The
 205 pre-episode VWC was computed as the mean value recorded by the four TDR sensors installed in the biofilter at
 206 the commencement of each rainfall-runoff episode. Runoff coefficients specific to each episode were calculated
 207 as the ratio of the volume of runoff to the volume of precipitation for given episode. In certain cases, multiple
 208 precipitation events were aggregated into a single episode. In sum, a total of 301 rainfall-runoff episodes were
 209 recorded, with total inflow depths varying from 1.1 to 47.8 mm, evaluated across five water years.

210 **Hydrological efficiency and stormwater runoff retention and delay**

211 The hydrological performance of bioretention systems is characterized by hydrological efficiency and water
212 retention effects (Gong et al., 2019; Meng et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2021). Hydrological efficiency is quantified
213 by two runoff coefficients: the annual runoff coefficient (R_{cy}), which encompasses the entirety of the water year,
214 and the episodic runoff coefficient ($\overline{R_{ce}}$), which is obtained as an average from the runoff coefficients (R_{ce})
215 calculated for each individual rainfall-runoff episode. These coefficients are demonstrated in Eq. (1).

$$R_{cy} = \frac{R_y}{I_y}; R_{ce} = \frac{R_e}{I_e} \quad (1)$$

216 Where R_y is total outflow and I_y is the total inflow over entire water year, while R_e is total outflow and I_e is total
217 inflow in for a singular rainfall-runoff episode, both R and I normalized to roof area. In contrast, water retention
218 (R_r) refers to the total amount of water retained by the system, as indicated by Eq. (2).

$$R_r = \frac{I - R}{I} \cdot 100\% \quad (2)$$

219 Where I is total inflow in episode (mm), R is total runoff in episode (mm) both normalized to roof area.

220 The peak flow reduction R_{pr} is shown in the ratio of rainfall peak intensity to runoff peak intensity according to
221 Eq. (3).

$$R_{pr} = \frac{I_p - R_p}{I_p} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

222 Where I_p is peak rainfall intensity (mm min^{-1}), R_p is peak runoff intensity (mm min^{-1}) during episode.

223 The term water retention is employed to describe the amount of water that is temporarily retained by the system,
224 as indicated by the runoff delay (ΔT_r) and peak runoff delay (ΔT_{pr}), as shown in Eq. (4) and Eq. (5).

$$\Delta T_r = T_I - T_R \quad (4)$$

225 T_I is the time the inflow appears, T_R is the time runoff appears.

$$\Delta T_{pr} = T_{Ip} - T_{Rp} \quad (5)$$

226 T_{Ip} is the time the runoff peak appears, T_{Rp} is the time inflow peak appears.

227 Certain episodes demonstrated negative runoff delays or negative peak runoff delays. These occurrences were
228 excluded from the analysis as they could be attributed to multiple rainfall events within the episode, potentially
229 causing the runoff peak to precede the rainfall peak. Evaluations of runoff delay and peak runoff delay were
230 restricted to episodes where inflow exceeded 3 mm or when a peak rainfall intensity of at least 0.3 mm min^{-1} was

231 observed. Episodes characterized by lower inflow and intensity exhibited runoff delays comparable to peak runoff
232 delays; therefore, such episodes were not included in the assessment. A peak runoff delay exceeding 1000 minutes
233 was classified as an outlier and omitted from the analysis. Additionally, episodes characterized by multiple rainfall
234 events potentially resulting in negative peak runoff delays were also excluded.

235 **Water balance equation**

236 The water balance equation for bioretention cell that is hydraulically isolated from surrounding soil is:

$$\Delta S = P + I - O - ET \quad (6)$$

237 Where P denotes the precipitation (mm) directly incident on the bioretention cell (BC), I represents the inflow
238 (mm) derived from the drainage roof, O signifies the outflow (mm) from the BC, ET corresponds to
239 evapotranspiration (mm), and ΔS indicates the change in water storage (mm). To ensure consistency, all variables
240 within the water balance are articulated in terms of depth (mm), referenced to the bioretention system area of 9.6
241 m². Interception is excluded from the balance equation because it pertains solely to direct precipitation on the
242 bioretention cell surface and does not involve roof inflow, thus it is considered negligible. Throughout the study
243 duration, no overflow beyond the system was observed. It is important to emphasize that precipitation assessments
244 conducted using a heated tipping bucket rain gauge with an area of 200 cm² may potentially exhibit a certain degree
245 of bias (Hoffmann et al., 2016). Significantly, during the winter months, a portion of precipitation may not be
246 captured as a result of the rain gauge heating mechanism being activated at temperatures of 5°C (Savina et al.,
247 2012), leading to an increased rate of evaporation of intercepted water droplets. Consequently, for periods when
248 the temperature dropped below 5°C, precipitation data were corrected using an augmentation factor of 1.2.
249 Additionally, precipitation data spanning April to October were adjusted with a roof runoff coefficient of 0.95,
250 specific to bitumen roofs (Lancaster, 2019). The evaluation of the water balance encompassed the entire water
251 year, commencing with an initial baseline value of zero. Daily fluctuations in water storage were calculated on a
252 daily time step. Average daily measurements from the four TDR sensors were extrapolated to the total biofilter
253 volume, under the assumption that the sand layer was fully saturated, and no water was present in the drainage
254 layer. The partial absence of data for WY20, WY21, and WY22 is attributed to the malfunctioning of rain gauges
255 or bucket flow meters at the outflow.

256 **Estimates of evapotranspiration**

257 The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) standardized Penman-Monteith equation, as outlined by Allen et
258 al. (1998), formulated for a reference crop of consistent height, was employed to determine the reference
259 evapotranspiration (ET_0):

$$ET_0 = \frac{0.408\Delta(R_n - G) + \gamma \frac{C_n}{T + 273} u_2 (e_s - e_a)}{\Delta + \gamma(1 + C_d u_2)} \quad (7)$$

260 where ET_0 is reference evapotranspiration in mm day^{-1} , R_n is net radiation flux ($\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$), G is soil heat flux
 261 density ($\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$), C_n is time step (for daily step is 900), C_d is crop height (0.34), T is mean air temperature at
 262 2 m height ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), u_2 is wind speed in 2 m height (m s^{-1}), e_s is saturation vapor pressure (kPa), e_a is actual vapor
 263 pressure curve (kPa K^{-1}), Δ is slope vapor pressure curve ($\text{kPa } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$) and γ is psychrometric constant ($\text{kPa } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$).
 264 For the daily step, the soil heat flux G is relatively small and may be zero.

265 The methodology advanced by the FAO elucidates crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) as the multiplicative result of the
 266 reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) and a crop coefficient (K_c), which serves to calibrate ET_0 to particular plant
 267 conditions. The designated values of K_c are specifically established for agricultural crops. To enhance the precision
 268 of ET_L estimation, a landscape coefficient, K_L , was employed to accommodate variables such as plant species, size,
 269 and microclimate. The landscape coefficient was determined based on a methodology proposed by Costello et al.
 270 (2000) and used, for example, in the studies by Selbig and Balster (2010) and Bortolini and Zanin (2018). This
 271 adjustment considers the unique water requirements of developing plants, as they generally require less water
 272 compared to mature vegetation. The revised equation for determining landscape evapotranspiration is as follows:

$$ET_L = ET_0 K_L \quad (8)$$

274 and K_L is determined:

$$K_L = k_s k_d k_{mc} \quad (9)$$

276 Where k_s is species factor k_d is density factor and k_{mc} is microclimate factor.

277 The K_L coefficient was utilized to estimate the landscape evapotranspiration, ET_L , from the beginning of April to
 278 the end of October in each year. Evapotranspiration from November to March was assumed to be minimal due to
 279 the dormancy of perennial vegetation and the existence of a gravel layer on the surface, which impeded
 280 evaporation. During this interval, a coefficient of 0.1 was applied to reduce ET_0 . In April, perennials were pruned,
 281 and biomass was removed, thus promoting growth recovery. The k_d , indicative of plant density, was adjusted in
 282 accordance with growth dynamics. The k_d value increased linearly from April 1 to June 30, attaining the value
 283 specified in Table 1. Photographs of the bioretention cell were subjected to semi-quantitative analysis employing
 284 ImageJ software (Abramoff et al., 2004) to assess plant growth metrics and ascertain the k_d coefficient. The

285 perspective of these photographs was adjusted utilizing the Interactive Perspective plugin (Schindelin et al., 2012),
 286 and their scale was modified accordingly. From these adjusted photographs, the fundamental widths of the plants
 287 were measured, which facilitated the calculation of the percentage of land coverage by the plants, thereby
 288 permitting the determination of the k_d coefficient. The final values of the K_L for each year are presented in Table
 289 1.

290 Table 1 Values of K_L coefficients for all water years in the period from 1.6. to 31.10.

	k_s (-)	k_d (-)	k_{mc} (-)	K_L (-)
Range of values	0.4 - 0.6	0.5 - 1.3	0.5 - 1.4	-
WY19	0.5	0.7	1	0.35
WY20	0.6	0.9	1	0.54
WY21	0.6	1.1	1	0.66
WY22	0.6	1.2	1	0.72
WY23	0.6	1.2	1	0.72

291

292 *Validation of landscape coefficient*

293 To assess the influence of the K_L factor on ET_0 , analyses RMSE and NSE were conducted. The cumulative water
 294 storage, denoted as ΔS and calculated through Eq. (10), was subsequently compared to S_{vwc} , which was obtained
 295 from volumetric water content (VWC) measurements captured by TDR sensors. The validation was conducted on
 296 daily values for each water year. Data gaps arising from missing measurements were omitted from the analysis,
 297 resulting in a range of 342 to 365 analytical steps. These analyses assessed the potential enhancement in accuracy
 298 achieved by incorporating vegetation data, derived from photographic sources, into the K_L coefficient, relative to
 299 the use of a traditional crop coefficient or a solitary constant coefficient. The RMSE and NSE are defined as:

$$300 \quad RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - S_{vwc_i})^2} \quad (10)$$

301 Where S_i water storage calculated from O , I and ET , S_{vwc} water storage demined from volumetric water content i
 302 is daily time step and n is number of steps,

$$303 \quad NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - S_{vwc_i})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_{vwc_i} - \mu)^2} \quad (11)$$

304 where μ is the mean of the S_{vwc} values.

305 **Biofilter and sand properties determined in laboratory**

306 The initial physical and chemical properties of the leachate, along with the hydraulic characteristics of the biofilter
 307 soil, have been documented by Heckova et al. (2022). The chemical composition of the leachate from the biofilter

308 was examined on two occasions. Disturbed soil samples were collected in October 2019 and October 2023 and
 309 subsequently analyzed in an external laboratory adhering to the European Committee for Standardization leaching
 310 protocol (EN 12457-4, 2002). The chemical properties are detailed in Supplementary Material Table S1, while the
 311 Total Organic Carbon (TOC) is presented in Table 2. Over the course of the study, soil samples were collected
 312 during five distinct sampling events for the purpose of assessing retention curves. The soil sampling events
 313 occurred on 24 May 2019, 15 November 2019, 17 June 2020, and 1 November 2023. During each sampling event,
 314 four undisturbed soil samples were acquired from four distinct locations, with each location being associated with
 315 a specific plant species, in order to measure retention curves that accurately reflect the conditions specific to each
 316 plant location. Concurrently, undisturbed samples were collected for μ CT analysis and results were presented
 317 recently by Heckova et al. (2024). Saturated hydraulic conductivity measurements were not performed on soil
 318 columns, as the procedure would have required larger cylinder diameters, thereby necessitating significant
 319 disruption to the biofilter upon their collection. The main drainage branch of the retention curve was ascertained
 320 using a standardized apparatus and methodology that incorporated a sand box and a pressure extractor (Soil
 321 Moisture Equipment Corp., Goleta, CA), as outlined by Klute (1986). In order to reduce the potential influence of
 322 outlier values, two of the four retention curves were excluded from the analysis for each sampling event.
 323 Specifically, these were the curves exhibiting the lowest θ_s and the curve exhibiting the highest θ_s . Subsequently,
 324 the van Genuchten parameters of the retention curve van Genuchten (1980), denoted as θ_r , θ_s , α , and n , were
 325 derived through the application of the non-linear least-squares method, utilizing measured retention data points
 326 and processed through the RETC code (van Genuchten et al., 1991). The van Genuchten parameters of the retention
 327 curve are delineated in Table 2.

328 Table 2 Retention curve characteristics of sand and biofilter

Date	θ_r (cm ³ cm ⁻³)	θ_s (cm ³ cm ⁻³)	α (-)	n (-)	Grain size distribution	TOC (%C)	Dry bulk density (g m ⁻³)
Biofilter							
01.12.2017	-	-	-	-	12% clay, 14% silt, 74% sand	-	-
18.11. 2018	0.024	0.447	0.094	1.274	-	-	1.37
24.05. 2019	0.108	0.404	0.127	1.176	-	-	1.41
15.11. 2019	0.160	0.408	0.044	1.251	-	2.95	1.37
17.06. 2020	0.093	0.423	0.157	1.166	-	-	1.42
01.11. 2023	0.097	0.381	0.019	1.347	12% clay, 18% silt, 70% sand	-	1.22
08.11. 2024	-	-	-	-	-	1.23	-
Sand							
01.11. 2023	0.000	0.422	0.110	1.448	4% clay, 1% silt, 95% sand	-	-

329

330 **Simulation of water flows in bioretention cell**

331 Two dimensional simulations of infiltration during rainfall events were conducted to interpret the observed
332 hydrological data. The HYDRUS 2D/3D (Version 5.04) (Šimůnek et al., 2024), employed for simulations, utilizes
333 numerical solutions of the Richards equation to address variably saturated flow in porous media. Airflow was
334 disregarded, and isothermal conditions were presumed. In this investigation, the model was calibrated using
335 measured cumulative outflow values and pressure heads derived from tensiometric measurements. The
336 concordance between the model and the simulation was evaluated using the Nash-Sutcliffe coefficient of efficiency
337 (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). Three study periods from the years 2019, 2020, and 2023 were identified for
338 hydrological modeling, during which retention curves were measured. These study periods were designed to span
339 approximately 14 days, with an inflow of approximately 40 mm. All study periods were conducted during the
340 summer months, specifically in August. The initial study period was conducted from August 11 to August 26,
341 2019 (SP19), the subsequent from August 2 to August 16, 2020 (SP20), and the final from August 5 to August 21,
342 2023 (SP23). Furthermore, the episodes were selected to ensure consistent initial biofilter conditions. The initial
343 conditions of the biofilters during episodes SP19 and SP23 were characterized by elevated moisture levels. The
344 initial pressure head for episode SP19 was recorded at -20 cm (T8_5), whereas for episode SP23, it was -30 cm
345 (T8_2). Conversely, episode SP20 demonstrated comparatively drier initial conditions, with a documented
346 moisture level of -400 cm (T8_2). Nevertheless, significant precipitation ensued shortly after SP20 began, resulting
347 in the saturation of the biofilter, thereby permitting comparative analysis with the other episodes. The ET_L was
348 modified from a daily step to a minute step. The inflow data was imported in minute increments and comprised of
349 two elements: water collected from the roof (implemented as variable flux 1 and atmospheric boundary condition)
350 and direct rainfall (variable flux 2) onto the bioretention cell surface.

351 *Flow domain and boundary conditions*

352 The model simplifies the flow domain by primarily assuming predominantly vertical water flow, as previously
353 demonstrated by Heckova et al. (2022), which facilitates the resolution of a two-dimensional simulation as opposed
354 to a more complex three-dimensional flow.

355 The boundary conditions and domain geometry are depicted in Fig. 4. Simulations were executed in a vertical
356 longitudinal central section of the system, where the bottom of BC was defined as an infiltration area with
357 dimensions of 2.6×1.5 meters. Diverse regimes were employed to simulate water inflow by integrating the inflow
358 originating from the roof with direct precipitation impacting the surface of the bioretention cell. The inflow was
359 oriented towards the bioretention cell from the left. It is hypothesized that uniform infiltration across the base of

360 the bioretention cell is achieved if the cumulative rainfall exceeds 1 mm within a two-hour period from the
 361 commencement of the rainfall event or if the rainfall intensity exceeds 0.3 mm per minute. Under such
 362 circumstances, it is presumed that the concrete tiles positioned at the center of the cell facilitate an even distribution
 363 of water across the entire infiltration surface. In the model, these conditions activate the atmospheric boundary
 364 condition with prescribed rain intensity and possibility of water accumulation at the surface. The section spanning
 365 30 cm on the left is characterized by a variable flux (variable flux 1) to replicate the initial flow through this section
 366 before the atmospheric condition is triggered. Rainfall infiltration along the inclined surfaces of the bioretention
 367 cell was established as a variable flux boundary condition (variable flux 2). The outflow of water from the
 368 bioretention cell was delineated using a seepage face condition across the left boundary of the drainage layer, with
 369 a maximum height of 10 cm. This height correlates to the diameter of the drainage pipe. Outflow was simplified
 370 in the model as it did not explicitly account for drainage through the pipe. Due to the exceptionally high
 371 conductivity of the drainage layer, no obstruction to drainage occurred. The water outflow was set at zero pressure
 372 on the seepage face.

373
 374 Fig. 4 The configuration of the longitudinal section of the bioretention cell, showing boundary conditions as utilized in the HYDRUS
 375 simulation.

376 *Evapotranspiration and root water uptake*

377 The root zone is prescribed as the region located beneath the infiltration surface of the bioretention cell (Fig. 4).
 378 The depth of the root zone was 30 cm, aligning with the depth of the biofilter below the bottom. The peak intensity
 379 of water uptake by roots in the vertical axis was identified at a depth of 20 cm. Over time, the horizontal expanse
 380 of the root zone progressively widened in accordance with the maturation of the plants, with the annual
 381 demarcations of this root zone illustrated in Fig. 4. The distribution of the root zone in HYDRUS (Vrugt et al.,
 382 2001) was parameterized as follows: In 2019, the width of the root zone was 260 cm, with the maximum root water
 383 uptake intensity at 100 cm. In 2020, the root zone expanded to 320 cm, with the maximum uptake intensity at 200
 384 cm. By 2023, the root zone reached a width of 400 cm, with the maximum root water uptake intensity increasing

385 to 260 cm. The total depth of the root zone remained constant for all periods. The initial condition for the simulation
386 was set using a linear distribution of pressure heads with depth, representing the assumed moisture conditions at
387 the start of the episodes.

388 The effects of water stress on root water uptake were modeled using the Feddes function (Feddes et al., 1978). The
389 "anaerobiosis point" (P0) was set to 0 cm, representing near-saturation conditions where water uptake is minimal.
390 Optimal water uptake occurred between pressure heads P_{Opt} (-1 cm H₂O) and P_{2H} (-500 cm H₂O) at a higher
391 potential transpiration rate (0.5 cm day⁻¹). For a lower potential transpiration rate (0.1 cm day⁻¹), the limiting
392 pressure head P_{2L} was set to -150 cm. If the pressure head dropped below the wilting point (P₃ = -9000 cm H₂O),
393 water uptake ceased entirely.

394 *Time variable hydraulic properties*

395 It was postulated that employing parameters measured during a particular year of the study would yield a more
396 accurate correspondence between the model and observational data, as compared to the use of a one set of
397 parameters for all modeled study periods (e.g., the initial measured van Genuchten parameters). This assumption
398 was tested by comparing the agreement between monitored and modeled cumulative outflow for different
399 parameter sets using the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient. Firstly, the measured van Genuchten parameters of
400 the retention curves presented in Table 2 sand and biofilter layers. Biofilter's K_s was set at an initial measured
401 value of 0.78 cm min⁻¹ for all simulation periods. The saturated hydraulic conductivity of the sand, which was not
402 directly measured was predicted using the Rosetta software (Schaap et al., 2001) as 0.483 cm min⁻¹. The saturated
403 hydraulic conductivity of the gravel layer was estimated to be approximately 3000 cm min⁻¹ in accordance with
404 Das (2010). The porosity of the gravel layer was assessed using standard values documented for gravel with a size
405 fraction of 8/16 mm (Filipovic et al., 2014; Freeze and Cherry, 1979). The van Genuchten parameters of the
406 retention curve for gravel layer were set as follows: $\theta_r = 0.000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\theta_s = 0.293 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $\alpha = 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $n = 2.5$
407 and $K_s = 3000 \text{ cm min}^{-1}$. The Mualem-Genuchten model (Mualem, 1976; van Genuchten, 1980) was employed for
408 the parameterization of hydraulic properties. During the initial phase of the simulation, the originally measured
409 hydraulic parameters were applied.

410 *Parameter optimization*

411 The optimization process aimed at minimization of an objective function that quantified the discrepancies between
412 observed and simulated values of outflow and pressure heads. The optimized parameters included van Genuchten
413 parameters α , n , and K_s for both the biofilter and sand layer. The probable values of these parameters were

414 estimated over the study period, with several scenarios examined to refine the initial estimates. The determined
 415 parameter ranges are specified as follows: the K_s for the sand layer varied from 0.01 to 0.5 cm min⁻¹, whereas the
 416 K_s for the biofilter spanned from 0.5 to 10 cm min⁻¹. Similarly, range of n for the biofilter was from 1.1 to 1.5, with
 417 α for the biofilter ranging from 0.01 to 0.5 cm⁻¹. The model was optimized for two key variables: cumulative
 418 outflow (Q) and pressure head (h) within the biofilter. The objective function is defined as:

$$O(\mathbf{b}) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_1} w_Q [Q_{obs}(t_i) - Q_{sim}(t_i, \mathbf{b})]^2 + \sum_{j=1}^{N_2} w_{h,j} [h_{obs}(z_j, t_k) - h_{sim}(z_j, t_k, \mathbf{b})]^2 \quad (12)$$

419 Where \mathbf{b} is a vector containing optimized parameters, Q_{obs} is the observed cumulative outflow at a specific time t_i ,
 420 while h_{obs} represent the observed pressure head at depth z_j and time t_k . Q_{sim} and h_{sim} are the simulated values of
 421 cumulative outflow and pressure head, respectively. The subscripts N1 and N2 denote the total number of
 422 observations for cumulative outflow and for pressure head measurements at different depths and times,
 423 respectively. The weighting factors w_Q and $w_{h,j}$ allowed individual adjustment of the contributions of different
 424 measured data points to the objective function. Specifically, w_Q applies to the cumulative outflow data, and $w_{h,j}$
 425 applies to the pressure head measurements at depth z_j .

426 Results and discussion

427 Estimates of ET based on vegetation monitoring

428 The estimated daily water storage (ΔS) within the bioretention cell system for each year, as derived from water
 429 balance evaluations, was compared to the actual water storage (S_{vwc}) determined from water content sensors. Given
 430 that the hydrological regime in the bioretention cell is predominantly affected by evapotranspiration, which is itself
 431 largely dependent upon the state of vegetation, a sensitivity analysis of the K_L parameter was conducted. Fig. 5
 432 illustrates the agreement between ΔS and S_{vwc} over the study years, as indicated by RMSE and NSE metrics. The
 433 findings depicted in Fig. 5 demonstrate that the K_L values, estimated based on an assessment of vegetation size
 434 through analysis of plant photographs, were proximate to the global minima of RMSE (or the global maxima of
 435 NSE) across the study years WY20, WY21, WY22, and WY23. These findings suggest that considering the growth
 436 of perennial plants specific to each growing season leads to more precise estimations of ET.

437 In the year WY19, there was no occurrence of global extremes in RMSE and NSE within the acceptable range of
 438 values K_L . This may be attributed to the uncertainty in evaluating the water balance, which will be elucidated
 439 subsequently.

440

441 Fig. 5 Effect of the landscape coefficient K_L value variations on the (a) RMSE between the cumulative water storage S_t calculated
 442 from and water storage S_{vwc} the values obtained from the TDR and (b) Nash-Sutcliffe coefficient (NSE) for the same comparison.
 443 The lines correspond to each water year (WY), with symbols indicating the K_L values used for HYDRUS model.

444 The estimated daily, ET_L (Fig. 6) reached up to 3 mm d^{-1} during the growing season, with the peak values recorded
 445 in WY22 and WY23, when the vegetation attained full maturity. The cumulative, ET_L for each specific year were
 446 as follows: WY19, 138 mm; WY20, 190 mm; WY21, 196 mm; WY22, 196 mm; and WY23, 204 mm. The mean,
 447 ET_L for each water year during the growing season were: WY19, 0.64 mm; WY20, 0.91 mm; WY21, 1.22 mm;
 448 WY22, 1.26 mm; and WY23, 1.7 mm. Evapotranspiration accounted for 7-11% of annual inflow and 9-16% of
 449 inflow during the growing season (April to November). In comparison with other studies, the application of the
 450 K_L coefficient was demonstrated to be an effective approach. Similar ET values were documented in the research
 451 conducted by Spraakman et al. (2022), where evapotranspiration within the bioretention cell was recorded between
 452 2.3 and 2.9 mm day^{-1} . Multiple research efforts on bioretention lysimeters have demonstrated higher estimated
 453 daily ET ranging between 2 and 4 mm day^{-1} (Denich and Bradford, 2010; Hess et al., 2017). In relation to these
 454 studies, evapotranspiration was markedly lower in our research probably due to the mulch layer covering the cell
 455 surface. The levels of evapotranspiration documented by Bortolini and Zanin (2018), who examined the dynamics
 456 of two rain gardens incorporating biofilters, were comparable to the findings acquired in our bioretention cell as
 457 the detected evapotranspiration spanned from 6% to 13% of the total inflow. findings were presented by Zhou and
 458 Guo (2022), who determined that evapotranspiration constituted 8.1% of the annual inflow. In the growing season,
 459 spanning from April to November, ET comprised between 9% to 17% of the inflow during that interval. The study
 460 by Selbig and Balster (2010) aligns with our findings, revealing that the percentage of ET ranged from 12% to
 461 19% during the growing season (April to November) within bioretention cells containing prairie vegetation
 462 characterized by clay or sand biofilter. Conversely, in bioretention cells planted with grass, the proportion of ET

463 to cumulative inflow was even higher, with values ranging from 19% to 25% Selbig and Balster (2010). De-Ville
464 et al. (2024) undertook experiments employing a K_c that fluctuated from 0.68 to 2.56, based on the three plant
465 types studied, which included a grass mixture and monocultures of *Deschampsia cespitosa* and *Iris sibirica*. Their
466 research advised a standard K_c value of 1.0 for bioretention systems. A K_c value of 1.0 is particularly suitable for
467 fully grown stands. In this study, particularly during the initial two years, the K_L coefficient proves more suitable
468 for the characterization of vegetation in its partial development stages. It is important to note that the use of a
469 default K_c of 1.0 may result in a slight overestimation of evapotranspiration during the first two years of the study.
470 This statement is supported by the results of a study by Nasrollahpour et al. (2022), who found that the effects of
471 vegetation and media on ET evolve with time, and the effect of vegetation on ET becomes the most prominent
472 factor over time.

473 Fig. 6 presents the water balance over a five-year period of the study, wherein positive values denote daily
474 precipitation and cumulative inflow, while negative values correspond to cumulative outflow and ET_L .
475 Additionally, the cumulative water storage is represented, with positive values indicating water accumulation and
476 negative values signifying a depletion relative to the start of the year. In WY19, runoff marginally surpassed
477 inflow, as illustrated in Fig. 6. Precipitation during WY19 was approximately 100-150 mm less than in later water
478 years. Despite the utilization of three rain gauges, the recorded rainfall seems underestimated, potentially due to
479 evaporation loss from the heated rain gauge (Hoffmann et al., 2016). In WY19, the bioretention cell's vegetation
480 was in the early stages of its second year of maturation, leading to reduced evapotranspiration and limited runoff
481 mitigation. In subsequent years (WY20 and WY23), the inflow consistently surpassed the outflow, with
482 cumulative water storage persistently exhibiting negative values throughout the growing season. This trend
483 indicates the stabilization of the system's hydrologic performance as vegetation cover increased, enhancing ET
484 and water retention in the biofilter. Cumulative water storage remained relatively stable from November to April,
485 except in WY21, where it briefly increased due to high rainfall. ET was uniformly distributed during the growing
486 season, with the peak values recorded between June and October.

487

488 Fig. 6 Water balance in bioretention cell during each year WY19 - WY23. The graphs contain cumulative inflow and outflow, rainfall
 489 and ET_L . All terms in the water balance are expressed in units of depth (millimeters), related to the area of the bioretention system.
 490 Cumulative water storage shows changes of water storage relative to the beginning of the year.

491 **Rainfall runoff episodes analysis**

492 Fig. 7 illustrates the episode-based rainfall-runoff relationships for five water years. Observed lack of outflow for
 493 low rain amounts is consistent with the findings of Davis (2008).

494

495 Fig. 7 A analysis of outflow and inflow for each rainfall-runoff episode. The data are fitted with a linear function in each water year.
 496 The initial volumetric water content for all rainfall-runoff episodes is represented using color-coded scheme.

497 Table 3 presents a summary of hydrological indices for the five water years, comprising the total annual runoff
 498 coefficient (R_{cy}), the episodic runoff coefficient ($\overline{R_{ce}}$), and the average pre-episode volumetric water content
 499 (VWC) for all rainfall-runoff episodes. The R_{cy} demonstrates a declining trend, commencing at 1.10 in WY19 and
 500 continuing to 0.85 in WY23, with values in the final three years (WY21, WY22 and WY23) displaying near-
 501 identical characteristics. Similarly, the episodic runoff coefficient $\overline{R_{ce}}$ demonstrates a decline from 0.71 ± 0.24 in
 502 WY19 to 0.57 ± 0.23 in WY23, with values consistently lower than R_{cy} and the decrease over time being less

503 pronounced. Additionally, the average pre-episode VWC demonstrates a slight decline, from 0.30 ± 0.03 in WY19
 504 to 0.25 ± 0.06 in WY23. This trend reflects a reduction in soil moisture availability prior to rainfall-runoff episodes
 505 due to increase in evapotranspiration from increasingly established plants.

506 Table 3 Annual runoff coefficient R_{cy} represents the value for the entire water year. The episodic runoff coefficient R_{ce} from rainfall-
 507 runoff episode and the average pre-episode volumetric water content are shown as mean values with standard deviations.

Water year	Annual runoff coefficient R_{cy}	Episodic runoff coefficient R_{ce}	Total number of episodes	Number of episodes < 1 mm	Average pre-episode VWC
WY19	1.10	0.71 ± 0.24	99	40	0.30 ± 0.03
WY20	0.91	0.64 ± 0.27	96	51	0.29 ± 0.05
WY21	0.84	0.60 ± 0.25	88	43	0.27 ± 0.04
WY22	0.87	0.58 ± 0.25	106	45	0.28 ± 0.04
WY23	0.85	0.57 ± 0.23	112	52	0.25 ± 0.06

508

509 The runoff coefficients during the episodes are affected by the pre-episode VWC of the biofilter (Table 3). At the
 510 commencement of episodes in WY19, the pre-episode VWC of the biofilter was high, with an average value of
 511 0.3, thereby supporting the assumption of minimal plant transpiration. In contrast, the average pre-episode VWC
 512 in other years was lower, attributed to increased vegetation growth and higher plant transpiration, which facilitated
 513 the drying of the biofilter between episodes (Yu et al., 2023). Compared to other years within the study, WY23
 514 exhibited the driest pre-episode conditions for certain episodes. This observation supports the findings of Lucke
 515 and Nichols (2015) and Zhang and Chui (2017), who stated that the effectiveness of water retention in bioretention
 516 cells is dependent on the pre-episode saturation level of the biofilter. The reduction in outflow is influenced by the
 517 biofilter's composition and thickness. A study by Shah et al. (2023) documented an 82-90% reduction in runoff,
 518 while another study reported a reduction range of 45-99% (Faust and Abraham, 2016). Our study demonstrates a
 519 substantially lower reduction in runoff mainly due to the isolation of the BC from adjacent soil and the lack of
 520 groundwater infiltration. Findings by Brown and Hunt (2012) indicate that an increased biofilter layer thickness
 521 results in greater runoff reduction. In our study, the biofilter thickness adhered to the minimum guidelines, also
 522 diminishing retention capacity. Shah et al. (2023) and Mai and Huang (2021) recommended the use of IWSZ to
 523 ensure maximum infiltration into the bedrock. In our bioretention cell system, runoff constitutes the principal
 524 component of the water balance, supplemented by a lesser extent of evapotranspiration. In the absence of an IWSZ,
 525 evapotranspiration accounts for the majority of water loss within the system. Owing to the isolation from the
 526 adjacent soil and the lack of exfiltration, the outcomes of the present study diverge from those observed in other
 527 research, such as Heasom et al. (2006), where evapotranspiration accounted for the predominant component of

528 water loss within the system. In their study, exfiltration, coupled with evapotranspiration, resulted in a reduction
529 of water volume by 50–90%. Another study by Li et al. (2009) reported losses ranging from 20-50% due to
530 exfiltration and evapotranspiration, with the biofilter having a thickness of 60-90 cm.

531 Fig. 8 presents the peak flow reduction, runoff delay, and peak runoff delay observed over a five-year period. The
532 most notable peak flow reduction was observed in the first year (WY19), with a reduction surpassing 75%. As the
533 study years progress, there is an observed increase in the variability of values. Nonetheless, the median values
534 remain above 80% for all years, demonstrating the bioretention cell's high efficiency in reducing peak flow across
535 the five-year period. Similar findings have been reported in various other studies. For instance, the study conducted
536 by Lucke and Nichols (2015) documented peak flow reductions ranging from 79.6% to 93.6%. Other studies have
537 reported comparable reductions, with values ranging between 84% and 95% at biofilter thicknesses of 60 cm and
538 90 cm, respectively. Shrestha (2018) also reported significant reductions in peak flows, reaching 91% at biofilter
539 thicknesses of 61 cm. In comparison with the findings of these studies, our data indicate that substantial peak flow
540 reduction is attainable even at the minimum required biofilter thickness of 30 cm. The evaluation period includes
541 the winter season (excluding snow events), thereby indicating that the winter season does not hinder the
542 bioretention cell's capability for peak flow reductions. In contrast to the findings of Muthanna et al. (2008), which
543 demonstrated a decline in bioretention cell efficiency from 42% to 27% during the winter season, our results
544 substantiate the consistent efficacy of the bioretention system. Similar effectiveness has also been reported in other
545 studies (Lucke and Nichols, 2015; Shrestha, 2018; Willard et al., 2017). The runoff delay is depicted in Fig. 8b.
546 Throughout a five-year observational period, runoff delays were observed to range from 0 to 600 minutes. Of
547 particular note is the trend in median values, which demonstrated a decline during the first three years, followed
548 by stabilization accompanied by increased variability. The runoff delay in bioretention is particularly important
549 for urban settings. The average runoff delay over five years was recorded at 57 minutes, which is one-fifth less
550 compared to the study by Shuster et al. (2017), which recorded an average runoff delay of 300 minutes for 233
551 episodes spanning over five years. However, the evaluated systems exhibited variations in their design, comprising
552 three rain gardens with filter media depths ranging from 45 cm to 50 cm, situated atop a 35 cm drainage layer. Liu
553 et al. (2014) similarly reported a runoff delay, documenting a range of 26 to 54 minutes, which varied according
554 to the type of rainfall event. This study utilized a biofilter with a thickness of 46 cm. As illustrated in Fig. 8c, the
555 peak runoff delay was greater than the runoff delay, ranging from 0 to 1000 minutes. Similarly to the runoff delay,
556 the median peak runoff delay exhibited a decline for the post three years followed by stabilization. If the peak
557 rainfall and runoff intensity are equal to the minimum resolution of the rain gauge and tipping bucket flowmeter,

562 the peak runoff delay will be equal to the runoff delay. The observed decline in median values for both runoff
 563 delay and peak runoff delay across the past three years can be attributed to the formation of preferential pathways
 564 correlated with vegetation growth (Archer et al., 2002; Shah et al., 2023; Tian et al., 2023; Virahsawmy et al.,
 565 2014).

562
 563 Fig. 8 For each episode, the following variables were determined: a) peak flow reduction b) runoff delay, and c) peak runoff delay.
 564 The upper and lower edges of the boxplot bodies represent the upper and lower quartiles of the observed values, while the
 565 extremes correspond to the maximum and minimum values. The line within the box indicates the median value.

566 Temporal changes of biofilter properties assessed by modeling

567 The findings of inverse modeling for the three study periods, SP19, SP20, and SP23, are illustrated in Fig. 9. These
 568 findings encompass a comparative analysis of the monitored and modeled outflow rates, cumulative outflows, and
 569 pressure heads. For SP19 and SP23, soil tensiometers T8_2 and T8_5 were employed for optimization purposes.
 570 Conversely, for SP20, tensiometers T8_2 and T8_3 were utilized, due to a 14-day data outage of tensiometer T8_5,
 571 which affected the SP20 episode.

572 Biofilter during SP19 shows a modeled pressure heads ranging from 0 to -51 cm, while physically measured ranged
 573 from 30 to -41 cm. The observed total cumulative runoff is consistent with the modelled runoff. The rainfall during
 574 SP19 was distributed in a uniform manner across four rainfall-runoff episodes of high intensity precipitation that
 575 occurred during the study period. The model overestimated peak discharge in case of the second high intensity
 576 rain episode.

577 At the beginning of SP20, the biofilter exhibited considerable dryness, with pressure heads registering below -300
 578 cm. Nonetheless, substantial rainfall was observed shortly after the initiation of the study, leading to the saturation
 579 of the biofilter. During SP20, precipitation was predominantly concentrated at the beginning and towards the end
 580 of the period, with a reduction in rainfall in the intermediary phase. Throughout SP20, three rainfall-runoff
 581 episodes were documented. The model underestimated the outflow following the drier phase. Specifically, the

582 model failed to accurately predict runoff in response to the minor precipitation episode on 10 August 2020.
583 Conversely, the model's estimation of the runoff for the rainfall event occurring between the 2nd and 5th of August
584 aligned closely with the empirically measured runoff.

585 The conditions of the biofilter during SP23 closely resembled those observed in SP19, characterized by elevated
586 water content and pressure head measurements fluctuating between 22 and -80 cm as per the model, while the
587 measured pressure head varied from 4 to -70 cm. The modeled cumulative outflow in SP23 demonstrated a
588 significant correlation with the cumulative measured outflow. Throughout the study period, three rainfall-runoff
589 episodes were recorded, with the concluding episode presenting the most intense rainfall.

590 The modeled cumulative runoff in SP23 and SP19 exhibited the highest degree of correlation with the measured
591 cumulative runoff among the three selected SPs. In both SP19 and SP23, where biofilter zero pressure head was
592 recorded during the SP, all runoff events were accurately captured. Likewise, in both SP19 and SP23, the model
593 consistently overestimated the actual peak runoff. Conversely, in SP20, the model better estimated peak runoff in
594 the initial third of the episode. Nevertheless, during periods of drought, the model's predictions of peak runoff
595 exhibited a reduced level of precision.

596

597 Fig. 9 Comparison of measured and modeled flows from bioretention cell BC1 over a 14-day period in August of 2019, 2020, and
 598 2023. The first row compares cumulative inflow, observed cumulative outflow, and modeled cumulative outflow. The second row
 599 shows the measured actual outflow, rainfall intensity, and modeled actual outflow. The last row provides a comparison of
 600 measured and modeled pressure heads, with T8_2 and T8_5 analyzed for SP19 and SP23, and T8_2 and T8_3 for SP20.
 601 Columns correspond to one study period.

602 The modelled pressure heads were systematically lower than the corresponding pressure heads measured by
 603 tensiometers during all three periods of the study. SP19 and SP23, which exhibited overall moist conditions,
 604 demonstrated the smallest discrepancy between the measured and observed pressure head values. In the SP20
 605 episode, there was a more significant underestimation of the modelled pressure heads. The differences in measured
 606 pressure heads from different tensiometers demonstrated an uneven distribution of pressure head within the
 607 biofilter, which can be attributed to the diverse plant root systems present within the biofilter. During episodes
 608 SP19 and SP23, the biofilter experienced wetter conditions. Under these conditions, the model exhibited better
 609 agreement with measured pressure head data. The model's sensitivity to minor rainfall events is diminished, similar
 610 to the findings reported by Stewart et al. (2017). Across all SPs, the model consistently underestimated pressure

611 head values. Nevertheless, the temporal patterns, trends, and the rate of decline in pressure heads within the model
612 were consistent with the empirical observations. Conversely, the study conducted by Stewart et al. (2017)
613 identified an overestimation of soil moisture within the biofilter, which was ascribed to preferential flow. The
614 observed underestimation of pressure head values might potentially be reduced by incorporating θ_s and θ_r into the
615 optimized parameters; however, this inclusion would result in an increase in the degrees of freedom within the
616 inverse solution. The representative value of θ_s was computed by averaging measurements on samples taken from
617 four distinct locations within the biofilter and subsequently scaled to represent the entire biofilter. The physically
618 determined θ_s , as presented in Table 2, stabilized in time at approximately $0.4 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ following the initial
619 consolidation of the biofilter. The obtained θ_s values can be compared with the development of macroporosity,
620 which was analyzed in the prior study by Heckova et al. (2024) utilizing μCT imaging. The development of
621 macroporosity was evaluated during the interval from June 18, 2018, to June 20, 2020, using μCT imaging. The
622 trend of macroporosity in the biofilter during 2018 - 2020 reveals dynamics that are comparable to those of the
623 measured θ_s values. Both parameters initially decreased as a result of soil consolidation, followed by a slight
624 increase attributed to the development of soil structure. The θ_s values can also be compared to total porosity, which
625 was evaluated in the same study by Heckova et al. (2024). The median value of total porosity decreased from 0.56
626 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ to $0.46 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Subsequent to the initial consolidation phase, the total porosity fluctuated around 0.46
627 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. In contrast, a minor decrease in the median values of total porosity was observed between May 19, 2019,
628 and June 2020. Nevertheless, it is anticipated that total porosity will stabilize and continue oscillating around the
629 post-consolidation value of $0.45 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

630 The inverse modeling of SP19, SP20, and SP23 facilitated the estimation of three distinct sets of hydraulic
631 properties, as illustrated in Table 4. The parameter α was estimated within a constrained range from 0.01 to 0.03,
632 while parameter n ranged from 1.3 to 1.5. Inverse modeling illustrated a gradual enhancement in the saturated
633 hydraulic conductivity within the biofilter over time. Initially, the values were closely consistent with the initial
634 levels, indicating that soil consolidation did not significantly influence the functionality of the bioretention cell.
635 This observation is congruent with the findings of other studies by Guo et al. (2018) and Zhang et al. (2024)
636 Additionally, Vineyard et al. (2015) observed that sediment accumulation did not markedly affect soil infiltration
637 during the initial decade of operation. The onset of root system development in 2019 catalyzed an augmentation
638 in hydraulic conductivity, a trend that continued in the ensuing years. Following a five-year period of operation,
639 hydraulic conductivity exhibited an increase of up to five times the initial value. This enhancement is ascribed to
640 the proliferation of the root system and the establishment of preferential pathways. This phenomenon of increased

641 hydraulic conductivity owing to plant roots aligns with the research outcomes of previous studies (Ebrahimian et
642 al., 2020; Hunt et al., 2008). However, the distinction between the years 2020 and 2023 was not as obvious. The
643 estimated K_s also correlated with a diminishing runoff delay as depicted in Fig. 9. The decrease of runoff coefficient
644 over time is attributed to enhanced plant transpiration and development of the root system. The 4% rise in the
645 fraction of silt particles within the biofilter over five years was not statistically significant and did not visibly
646 produce clogging. Conversely, the estimated hydraulic conductivity of sand evidenced a decline, potentially
647 attributable to the leaching of fine particles from the biofilter. However, initial values concerning grain size
648 distribution were not available for analysis. In the course of inverse modeling, the correlation coefficient between
649 the saturated hydraulic conductivity of sand and the biofilter was determined to be less than 0.5, indicating the
650 independence of these parameters. This independence thereby enhances the reliability and transparency of the
651 inverse modeling results. Moreover, the increase in hydraulic conductivity of biofilter and the influence of the root
652 system on biofilter efficacy have been substantiated in numerous previous studies (Shah et al., 2023; Shrestha,
653 2018; Virahsawmy et al., 2014).

654 Table 4 Optimized van Genuchten parameters α , n , K_s of biofilter and K_s of sand layer of the retention curve and saturated
655 hydraulic conductivities of sand and biofilter layers

	Layer	α (1 cm ⁻¹)	n (-)	K_s (cm min ⁻¹)
2019 SP19	Biofilter	0.015	1.402	1.087
	Sand	-	-	0.209
2020 SP20	Biofilter	0.03	1.310	3.042
	Sand	-	-	0.234
2023 SP23	Biofilter	0.030	1.340	4.591
	Sand	-	-	0.054

656

657 Table 5 illustrates the Nash-Sutcliffe efficiency coefficients, which serve as indicators of the concordance between
658 modelled and observed runoff. This table evaluates the original measured parameters presented in Table 2, the
659 optimized parameters outlined in Table 4, as well as estimated K_s . Utilizing the original parameter sets, the model
660 demonstrated reasonably good agreement, with the highest level of agreement observed in episode SP19 for both
661 cumulative and actual runoff. On the other hand, the minimum coefficient observed when employing the original
662 parameters was recorded in episode SP23, which can be attributed to the hydraulic conductivity value in the
663 original parameter set being approximately five times greater than the optimized value for SP23. This discrepancy
664 likely resulted in larger deviations between the modelled and measured runoff. In contrast, for SP19, the optimized

665 K_s value was nearly identical to the value in the original parameter set, which contributed to the higher agreement
 666 of model and observations. The Nash-Sutcliffe coefficients for instantaneous runoff, while lower than 0.8 for both
 667 optimized and original parameters, suggest that the model exhibits reduced accuracy in capturing short-term
 668 fluctuations in runoff dynamics. They showed the highest agreement during the SP19 episode. Using the measured
 669 parameter sets from each year showed better agreement, except for SP20 where differences between the
 670 coefficients were noticeable but not significant.

671 Table 5 Nash–Sutcliffe model efficiency coefficients for cumulative outflow/actual outflow rate for three modeled episode and
 672 different original RETC parameters.

Modelling strategy	SP19	SP20	SP23
optimized, α , n and K_s	0.996/0.802	0.971/0.469	0.998/0.473
2019 lab. determined parameter set	0.992/0.759	0.947/0.365	0.814/0.380
2020 lab. determined parameter set	0.991/0.690	0.937/0.380	0.813/0.471
2023 lab. determined parameter set	0.991/0.720	0.853/0.405	0.834/0.457

673
 674 The model with optimized parameters demonstrated a strong agreement with the measured values of cumulative
 675 outflow. The model attained higher accuracy in episodes where rainfall was distributed uniformly and the biofilter
 676 pressure head was near zero (wet conditions). Conversely, the model's agreement with data was lower in episode
 677 SP20, which was distinguished by a prolonged period without rain and accelerated drying.

678 The NSE values demonstrate that the correlation of the model with cumulative runoff exceeds that of actual
 679 outflow rates. Following parameter optimization, the model demonstrated an NSE value exceeding 0.97, indicating
 680 a high degree of effectiveness under optimized conditions.

681 Conclusions

682 This study provides an evaluation of the long-term hydrological function of a pilot-scale experimental bioretention
 683 cell without exfiltration over a period of five years. The analysis of rainfall-runoff episodes demonstrated that the
 684 bioretention cell progressively enhances its ability to retain and delay stormwater runoff. The annual runoff
 685 coefficient decreased by up to 25% from initial values in subsequent years, primarily due to the establishment of
 686 perennial vegetation and increased evapotranspiration. Throughout the study period, the median reduction in peak
 687 flow exceeded 84%, with the variability of peak flow reduction increasing over the last three years. The system
 688 displayed an average runoff delay of approximately 57 minutes, with an average peak runoff delay of 120 minutes.

689 Evapotranspiration accounted for 7–11% of the annual inflow. Incorporating a landscape coefficient, estimated
690 semi-quantitatively from photographic documentation to account for vegetation growth and density, resulted in
691 improved estimates of evapotranspiration, especially during the initial two years of vegetation establishment.
692 Numerical modeling of water flow using HYDRUS 2D yielded satisfactory agreement between measured and
693 simulated cumulative outflow. However, the model exhibited reduced accuracy for low precipitation events
694 occurring during antecedent dry periods. Additionally, the modeled pressure heads were systematically
695 underestimated. Employing retention curve parameters, determined in the laboratory on undisturbed samples
696 collected in the corresponding year, led to a better correlation between model and data compared to using a single
697 parameter set for multiple years. The best agreement between the experimental data and the model was obtained
698 through year specific model calibration by inverse modeling. During the evaluation period, the hydraulic
699 conductivity (K_s) of the biofilter increased fivefold, attributed to the development of root system macroporosity.
700 Conversely, the K_s of the sand layer experienced nearly a fourfold reduction during the observation period.

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710 **Petra Maresova:** Data curation, Writing – original draft. **Michal Snehota:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
711 Writing – editing, Formal analysis, Supervision, Project administration.

712 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

713 The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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